

The Role of Digital Transformation in Financial Services Management and Its Impact on Iraqi Banking Sector

Dhamyaa Ghazi Hameed¹, Shaymaa Tareq Majon²

^{1,2}Ministry of Communication, Post & Saving public Company, Baghdad, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

This study derives its **importance** from the growing need to embrace digital transformation in the Iraqi banking sector by highlighting the role of digital financial services management in improving the quality of banking services, reducing costs, and increasing speed of delivery. The research also contributes to providing a knowledge base that decision-makers can rely on to develop financial and technical policies within Iraqi banking institutions.

This research **aims** to analyse the reality of digital transformation in the Iraqi banking sector and measure the impact of digitization and management of financial services on improving performance efficiency and the quality of banking services. It also seeks to explore the opportunities and challenges of implementing digital solutions in the local banking environment and propose practical mechanisms to enhance the use of financial technology, contributing to the development of the banking system and achieving sustainability and growth. The research **problem** stems from the fundamental question: To what extent has the digitization and modern management of financial services impacted the performance and efficiency of Iraqi banks? Most local banks suffer from a slow digital transformation and a weak adoption of modern tools, which may limit their competitiveness. The research hypothesis is based on the following: There is a statistically significant positive relationship between digitization and management of financial services and improved performance in the Iraqi banking sector." And Result the degree of agreement reached 76%, which is a reasonable percentage, as it constitutes (45%:45%) for agree and strongly agree, respectively. As for the answers regarding neutral, it reached 21%, while the degree of disagreement reached 9%, as it constitutes (5%:4%) for disagree and strongly disagree, respectively.

Corresponding Author:
Dhamyaa Ghazi Hameed

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1. INTRODUCTION

The world today is witnessing a radical transformation in the way financial services are delivered, driven by rapid developments in information and communications technology. Digitization has become a key factor in improving the efficiency of banking operations and providing easier, safer, and faster financial services. Banking institutions in many countries have adopted advanced digital systems to meet customer needs, enhance competitiveness, and ensure sustainability in an increasingly unstable financial environment. Iraqi banks face significant challenges and multiple opportunities as they strive to keep pace with this digital transformation (Khamis Aser Ahmed, 2023). The application of digitization in financial services goes beyond improving the customer experience; it also encompasses a comprehensive restructuring of management

mechanisms, controlling risks, enhancing transparency, and reducing operating costs. Digitization and the management of financial services in the Iraqi banking sector are vital topics at the current stage, especially in light of the government's drive towards digital transformation and the rising societal aspirations for the provision of advanced and secure digital banking services (Latif & Eltayeb, 2009). Digitization is known as process of converting data, information, and services from paper or traditional forms into digital form using modern computing and communication technologies. This process aims to improve operational efficiency, facilitate access to services, reduce costs, and enhance institutional performance (Amin, 2022). Banking can be defined as follows: Digitization in the banking sector refers to the use of digital technology to deliver financial and banking services electronically, such as

online banking transactions, smartphone applications, and smart ATMs. This process aims to enhance customer experience, improve operational efficiency, and reduce reliance on paper transactions (Ayman & Wafaa, 2023) and Digital transformation: The process through which the use of digital technologies changes the business model and provides new possibilities for generating value and revenue (Alnoor Bhimani, Charles T. Hornngren, Srikant M. Datar, & Madhav V. Rajan, 2023).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The Origin and Concept of Digitization: Digitization dates back to the mid-twentieth century, with the advent of the first computers, which enabled the conversion of analogy data into digital data. Digitization began as a technology used for archiving information and processing data within organizations. However, with the rapid development of information and communications technology, this technology began to take on broader dimensions, encompassing most areas of life (Abdel Wahid, Al-Kateb, & Tijani, 2024).The 1980s and 1990s witnessed significant developments in software and networks, leading to the widespread use of digital systems in the education, administration, health, and economic sectors. With the beginning of the twenty-first century, digitization emerged as a pivotal strategy for improving institutional performance, particularly in the financial and banking sectors, through the use of the internet, smartphones, and electronic service platforms. In the banking context, banks around the world have gradually adopted digitization through services such as automated teller machines (ATMs), electronic transfers, online accounts, and mobile phone applications (Al Said, 2024). Today, digitization has become a fundamental requirement for any modern banking system aimed at enhancing efficiency, expanding the customer base, and achieving financial innovation. As for digital transformation Digital transformation refers to the use of computer and internet technology to create more efficient and effective economic value. It is defined as a process of fundamental changes within a company's value chain or internal structure, which is either a cause or a prerequisite for the use of technology. The topic of digital transformation is addressed extensively in conjunction with new strategic concepts, particularly digital business strategy and digital transformation strategy. The central idea of digital business strategy is to understand information technology as a prerequisite for innovation and competitiveness (Al-Arabi & Abdel Aal, 2023). It is a process aimed at improving entities and organizations by initiating significant changes in their characteristics using combinations of information, computing, and communications technologies (Al-Mutairi, 2022).

2.2. Digital Transformation Goals: (Ibrahim & Issa, 2024).

- Promoting and developing a more creative and collaborative culture within bank and society.
- Changing the education system to provide new skills and future guidance for employees so they can achieve excellence in digital work and society.
- Establishing and maintaining digital communications infrastructure and ensuring its governance, accessibility, quality of service, and affordability.
- Enhancing digital data protection, transparency, independence, and trust.
- Improving accessibility and the quality of digital services provided.
- Implementing new and innovative business models to achieve the goal.
- Working to implement innovative business models and improve the regulatory framework and technical standards.

2.3. Stages of Digital Transformation: Most literature has discussed the three stages of digital transformation, as follows:

- ❖ **Digitalization and Modelling:** represents the first stage, which refers to the encoding of analog information into a (digital) format, i.e., into zeros so that computers can store, process, and transmit this information. Digitization refers to the transformation of analog tasks into digital ones, or its conceptualization as the integration of information technology with existing tasks, and more broadly, as the development or enabling of cost-effective resource configurations using information technology. Based on the above, digitization is defined to describe the process of converting analog information into digital information. Examples include the use of digital models in ordering processes, the use of digital surveys, or the use of digital applications for internal financial advertising. Digitization typically primarily digitizes internal and external document processes, but it does not change value-creation activities (Muehlburger, M., Rueckel, D. & Koch, S., 2019).
- ❖ **Visual Digitization:** The second stage of digital transformation, the visual digitization stage, reflects how information technology or digital technologies are used to change existing business processes, such as creating new online or mobile communication channels that allow all customers to easily connect with businesses, transforming traditional interactions between partners and customers that would not have been possible without digital technologies. Through digitization,

banks apply digital technologies to improve existing business processes by allowing for more effective coordination between processes and/or by creating additional value for customers through enhanced user experiences (Lieberman, A. Paravisini, D. & Pathania, V., 2018).

- ❖ **Digital Transformation:** is the most prevalent stage, describing company-wide change that leads to the development of new business models, which may be new to leading companies or the industry as a whole. Companies compete to achieve a competitive advantage through their business models, as well as through the way they create and deliver value to customers, and then convert the revenues generated from using digital processes into profits. Digital transformation introduces a new business model by applying new business logic to create and preserve value. Digital transformation impacts the entire organization and the way it conducts business. Digitization goes beyond visual representation, changing simple organizational processes and tasks (Al-Mutairi, 2022). It reorganizes processes to change the company's business logic or value creation process. For example, digital transformation in the healthcare sector manifests itself through the widespread and profound use of information technology, which fundamentally changes the delivery of healthcare services. The use of IT is transformative and leads to fundamental changes in existing business processes, procedures, and capabilities, allowing healthcare providers to enter or exit new markets (Pagani, M. & Pardo, C, 2017).

2.4. The Concept of Financial Services: Financial services are of paramount importance in financially dependent business activity, as finance determines the type of business activity. Financial services are defined as the art and science of managing money, encompassing financial services and instruments. A financial service is not the financial commodity itself, such as a mortgage loan for a home purchase or a car insurance policy, but rather the process of obtaining the financial commodity. that is, it involves the transaction required to obtain the financial service. The financial sector encompasses many different types of transactions, such as real estate, consumer finance, banking, and insurance. It also covers a wide range of investment financing, including securities (Ahmed, 2023) Financial services are mechanisms for obtaining financial services, including lending, insurance, capital management, retirement savings, securities trading, money transfers, and more. There are two sources of financial services:

- **First: The Banking Sector**
- **Second: Non-banking Financial Services:** Non-banking financial institutions serve as a source of financing for start-ups or newly established companies that do not have the collateral required by banks. Non-banking financial institutions represent companies in capital markets, insurance, contractual savings, real estate financing, financial leasing, and factoring (Talhi & Zawadi, 2023).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Descriptive Analysis: The research sample will be two banks, as follows:

- ❖ **The National Bank of Iraq (NBI):** is a private Iraqi bank, established in 1995. It provides financial and banking services to individuals and companies. It is a strategic partner of Qatar National Bank (QNB), providing financial support and international expertise. It offers modern banking services, such as a mobile application, MasterCard and Visa cards, personal and housing loans, and support for small and medium-sized enterprises.
- ❖ **Middle East Bank (MEB):** is a private Iraqi bank, established in 1993. It focuses primarily on investment and finance, helping finance economic projects, providing credit facilities (loans, financing), and various types of bank accounts (current and savings), as well as services related to trade and import. In this context, the field aspect will be enhanced by examining the Role of digital transformation in financial services management and its impact on the Iraqi banking sector. This was conducted by researchers at National Bank of Iraq (NBI) and the Middle East Bank (MEB) as the study sample population. The questionnaire was administered by posing a series of questions and inquiries to all employees and workers in private banks. These answers were analysed and interpreted using statistical programs, including the program, and the final results of the study were extracted.

3.2. Questionnaire Validity Test: Validity in research or studies lies in the suitability of the questionnaire and the consistency of the hypotheses formulated to achieve the study objectives, its reliance on it, and its distribution to the study sample.

3.3. Questionnaire Reliability Test: Reliability in a questionnaire refers to the stability of the scale and its lack of self-contradiction. This means that the scale produces the same results with a probability equal to the coefficient value when reapplied to the same population. The goal is to ensure the stability of the measurement used. The results of Cronbach's alpha

correlation coefficient were extracted, and the study data were entered into the SPSS statistical program to determine the accuracy of the study sample members' answers. For the statistical results of Cronbach's alpha to be accepted, the acceptable statistical percentage must be equal to or greater than 60%, which is considered a scientific reliability test, particularly for

social studies, financial and banking sciences, or management. The table below shows the values of Cronbach's alpha at the overall level of the study variables, which amounted to (5) questions for the first part, which is demographic data, and (13) questions for the second part related to the study axes

Table1. Cronbach's Alpha Correlation Coefficient at the Overall Level of Variables

Cronbach's alpha Correlation Coefficient	Factor-based reliability Coefficient	Number of Variables
0.9268	0.91	5
0.9488	0.95	13

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

From above table, we note that Cronbach's alpha correlation coefficient value reached **0.9268**, which is equal to 92% for demographic data, and **0.9488**, which is equal to 95%. These

are very high percentages, indicating positivity and reliability, and can be relied upon. Table below shows total axes of the study.

Table2. Cronbach's alpha correlation coefficient at overall level of variables (Three Axes)

Axes	Cronbach's alpha Correlation Coefficient	Factor-based reliability Coefficient	Number of Variables
Axis One	0.940	0.91	5
Axis Two	0.923	0.88	5
Axis Three	0.970	0.92	3

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

From aforementioned table, we note that all five axes' values are reliable, appropriate, and provide a clear and strong statistical significance. This is because all five axes' values are greater than 0.60, i.e., 60%. This confirms the stability and validity of the study's variables, making the results of questionnaire's responses reliable, whether within each axis

or across the three axes as a whole. Second: Analysing and Testing the Study's Hypotheses: researchers used a five-point Likert scale to measure responses to the questionnaire items. Table below shows weighted average for five-point Likert scale and its corresponding level.

Table3: Five-point Likert Scale Weighted Average

Alternatives	weighted average
Strongly Disagree	1.31
Disagree	1.27
Neutral	.243
Agree	16.51
Strongly agree	14.12

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

To determine the sample's response trends for each of the study's axes, (percentages, weighted average, arithmetic mean, frequencies, and standard deviation) were used. The results were as follows:

Axis One: Importance of Digital Transformation of Financial Services

Table4. Digital Transformation of Financial Services

Alternatives	Number	Percentage	Arithmeticmean	Standard deviation
Strongly Disagree	3	0.024		
Disagree	5	0.043		
Neutral	6	0.050	4.00	0.130
Agree	48	0.392		
Strongly agree	58	0.491		
Total	120	%100		

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

Figure1. Representation of answers (Percentages, Arithmetic means) Axis One

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

Second axis: Impact of Digital Transformation on banking performance

Table 5. Impact of Digital Transformation on Banking Performance

Alternatives	Number	Percentage	Arithmeticmean	Standard deviation
Strongly Disagree	4	0.025		
Disagree	5	0.051		
Neutral	21	0.166	3.6	0.57
Agree	45	0.384		
Strongly agree	45	0.374		
Total	120	%100		

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

Figure2. Impact of Digital Transformation on Banking Performance

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

For all of the above, the degree of agreement is consistent and consistent among the researched sample, as the degree of agreement reached 76%, which is a reasonable percentage, as it constitutes (45%:45%) for agree and strongly agree, respectively. As for the answers regarding neutral, it reached 21%, while the degree of disagreement reached 9%, as it constitutes (5%:4%) for disagree and strongly disagree, respectively.

Third axis: Challenges and obstacles

Table6. Challenges and Obstacles

Alternatives	Number	Percentage	Arithmeticmean	Standard deviation
Strongly Disagree	5	0.041	1.60	0.23
Disagree	7	0.059		
Neutral	26	0.216		
Agree	52	0.434		
Strongly agree	30	0.250		
Total	120	%100		

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

Figure3. Challenges and Obstacles

Source: Prepared by researchers based on annual reports of Banks (NBI & MEB)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: Testing the Study Hypotheses

❖ **First Hypothesis:** importance of Digital Transformation of Financial Services.

Table7. Correlation Coefficient between Importance of Digital Transformation and Financial Services

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Stud Error of other factors
1	0.750^a	0.652	0.569	0.58177

Source: Prepared by researchers

The simple correlation coefficient R is 0.750a, the coefficient of determination R Square is 0.652, and the corrected coefficient of determination is 0.569, meaning that

the independent variation coefficient explained 56.9% of the changes that occurred in the evaluation, while 0.58177 is attributed to other factors.

Table 8. Coefficient of variation between Importance of Digital Transformation and Financial Services

Model	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	33.923	1	33.921	100.229	0.000 ^b
1 Residual	26.398	115	0.340	-	-
Total	60.321	116	-	-	-

Source: Prepared by researchers

Table 9. Linear Regression Coefficient between Importance of Digital Transformation and Financial Services

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	1.401	0.224		06.272	0.000
1 Importance of Digital Transformation of Financial Services.	0.592	0.590	0.750	10.012	0.000

Source: Prepared by researchers

We note from the previous table that the second statistical significance test and the values of the regression coefficient, and from a statistical point of view, we note that the

independent variable has a significant effect according to the T-test (at the significance level $P \leq 0.05$). Since the linear regression equation is: $Y=1.401+0.592X$.

❖ **Second Hypothesis: impact of digital transformation on banking performance**

Table10. Correlation Coefficient between impacts of Digital Transformation on Banking Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Stud Error of other factors
1	0.796^a	0.633	0.528	0.53354

Source: Prepared by researchers

The simple correlation coefficient R is **0.796^a**, coefficient of determination R Square is **0.633**, and corrected coefficient of determination is **0.528**, meaning that the independent

variation coefficient explained 56.9% of the changes that occurred in the evaluation, while **0.53354** is attributed to other factors.

Table11. Coefficient of variation between Impacts of Digital Transformation on Banking Performance

Model	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	38.118	1	38.128	134.008	0.000 ^b
1 Residual	23.382	116	00.287	-	-
Total	61.500	117	-	-	-

Source: Prepared by researchers

Table12. Linear Regression Coefficient between impacts of Digital Transformation on Banking Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	1.401	0.224		06.272	0.000
1 impacts of Digital Transformation on Banking Performance	0.592	0.590	0.750	10.012	0.000

Source: Prepared by researchers

We note from the previous table that the second statistical significance test and the values of the regression coefficient, and from a statistical point of view, we note that the

independent variable has a significant effect according to the T-test (at the significance level of $P \leq 0.05$). Since the linear regression equation is: $Y = 1.401+ 0.592X$

❖ **Third Hypothesis: Challenges and obstacles**

Table13. Correlation Coefficient between Challenges and Obstacles

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Stud Error of other factors
1	0.797^a	0.635	0.528	0.53356

Source: Prepared by researchers

The simple correlation coefficient R is **0.797^a**, coefficient of determination R Square is **0.635**, and corrected coefficient

of determination is **0.528**, meaning that the independent variation coefficient explained 56.9% of the changes that

occurred in the evaluation, while 0.53356 is attributed to other factors.

Table14. Coefficient of variation between Challenges and obstacles

Model	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	39.118	1	39.118	134.008	0.000 ^b
1 Residual	22.382	114	00.288	-	-
Total	61.500	115	-	-	-

Source: Prepared by researchers

Table15. Linear Regression Coefficient between Challenges and Obstacles

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	1.302	0.227		06.272	0.000
1 Challenges and Obstacles	0.692	0.589	0.750	10.012	0.000

Source: Prepared by researchers

We note from the previous table that the second statistical significance test and the values of the regression coefficient, and from a statistical point of view, we note that the independent variable has a significant effect according to the T-test (at the significance level of $P \leq 0.05$). Since the linear regression equation is: $Y = 1.302 + 0.692X$

5. CONCLUSION

- There is a statistically significant positive relationship between digitization and management of financial services and improved performance in the Iraqi banking sector
- the degree of agreement reached 76%, which is a reasonable percentage, as it constitutes (45%:45%) for agree and strongly agree, respectively. As for the answers regarding neutral, it reached 21%, while the degree of disagreement reached 9%, as it constitutes (5%:4%) for disagree and strongly disagree, respectively
- The independent variable has a significant effect according to the T-test (at the significance level of $P \leq 0.05$). Since the linear regression equation is: $Y = 1.302 + 0.692X$

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REFERENCES

1. Abdel Wahid, A. O., Al-Kateb, M. B., & Tijani, A.-T. H. (2024). Commercial Banks' Policies for Financing Small Enterprises in the Digital Age in the City of N'Djamena, 2020-2022. *Faculty of Economics, King Faisal University, Chad*, 1-34.
2. Al-Arabi, M. A., & Abdel Aal, M. M. (2023). Rebuilding the competencies of local government human resources from the perspective of digital transformation policies: A comparative study between the Arab Republic of Egypt and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Studies Journal*, 24(1), 264-304.
3. Al-Mutairi, M. A. (2022). The Role of Digital Transformation Mechanisms in Assessing the Creditworthiness of Kuwaiti Business Companies: A Field Study. *The Scientific Journal of Financial and Administrative Studies and Research*.
4. Ayman, B., & Wafaa, H. (2023). Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) as a New Trend in Financial and Banking Transactions. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 90-112.
5. Ibrahim, M. M., & Issa, S. O. (2024). The Role of the Central Bank of Iraq in Promoting Digital Transformation and the Use of FinTech in Iraq for the Period 2017-2023. *Journal of Administration and Economics*, 136-143.
6. Khamis Aser Ahmed. (2023). The Impact of Digital Transformation on the Recruitment Strategy in the Egyptian Banking Sector: An Experimental Study. *Journal of Commerce and Finance*, 495-522.
7. Latif, T. A., & Eltayeb, D. (2009). Developing the Islamic banking industry under the financial and banking services liberalization agreement - with reference to the case of Algeria -. *University of Mohamed Khider - Biskra* -.
8. Talhi, K., & Zawadi, N. (2023). The role of Fintech innovations in the development of Islamic financial services-Kuwait finance house as a model-. *Journal of Studies in Islamic Finance and development*.
9. Youssef, B., & Osama, A. (2024). The Inevitability of Digitization and the Competitiveness of

- Financial Institutions in Gaining Customer Satisfaction: A Field Study of the National Bank of Algeria (BNA), Tiaret Agency. *Faculty of Economics, Business and Management Sciences*, 1-101.
10. Abboud, N. A., & Abbas, S. A. (2023). Credit Risk Analysis in Financial Performance for the Period 2010-2020: Gulf Commercial Bank as a Model. *Iraqi Journal of Economic Sciences*, 352-372.
 11. Abdelraheem, A. (2024). The Effect Of Capital Structure On Financial Performance. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 1879-1884.
 12. Ahmed, H. M. (2023). The Relationship Between Digital Transformation and Financial Services. *Scientific Journal of Business Research*, 4(1).
 13. Al Said, S. b. (2024). Banking Financial Transactions of Muslim Communities: A Comparative Jurisprudential Study. *Journal of Educational and Human Studies, Faculty of Education, Damanhour University, Volume 16, Issue 4, Part 1*, 626-684.
 14. Al-Awadly, R. H., & Washwasha, A. A.-M. (2023). The Role of Financial Intelligence in the Relationship between Behavioral Factors and Investment Decisions (An Applied Study). *Scientific Journal of Financial and Commercial Studies and Research*, 20-21.
 15. Alnoor Bhimani, Charles T. Horngren, Srikant M. Datar, & Madhav V. Rajan. (2023). MANAGEMENT AND COST ACCOUNTING. In Alnoor Bhimani, Charles T. Horngren, Madhav V. Rajan, Srikant M. Datar, & E. Edition (Ed.), *MANAGEMENT AND COST ACCOUNTING* (p. 810). New Jersey, USA: Pearson Education Limited.
 16. Al-Qahri, A. (2017). Determinants of Financial Reporting Quality and Its Impact on Financial Performance in Economic Institutions: A Comparative Study of a Sample of Foreign and Algerian Institutions. *University of Mohamed Khider, Biskra, Faculty of Economics, Business, and Management Sciences*, 55-70.
 17. Al-Rawazeq, A. S., Kazem, H. K., & Al-Amri, A. S. (2020). The Impact of Financial Intelligence Qualifications on Capital Development of Small and Medium Enterprises in Iraq. *Al-Rafidain Development Journal*, 12-22.
 18. Al-Shammari, A. J. (2022). The Impact of Corporate Financial Performance on the Real Value of Shares within the Framework of the Accounting Evaluation Model: An Applied Study in the Iraq Stock Exchange. *Technical Administrative College*, 22-32.
 19. Amin, M. R. (2022). Mechanisms for digitizing financial and banking services to establish digital financial inclusion - adopting financial technology innovations - as a way. *ASJP Economic studies*, 641- 626.
 20. ASADI, S. K. (2021). THE RATIONALIZATION VS THE REDUCTION OF REAL COSTS UNDER THE MODERN AGRICULTURE. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 164-174. doi:10.34218/IJM.12.4.2021.016
 21. Brizat, A. I. (2022). The Impact of Human Resource Expenditures on Financial Performance Indicators in Public Joint Stock Industrial Companies: The Moderating Role of Corporate Governance. *journal of Jerash University*, 45-55.
 22. Fernando, J. (2024). Compound annual growth rate (CAGR): How reinvesting your profits at the end of the year can impact your investments. *Investopedia*, 2-4.
 23. Imran, Q. J. (2022). The Impact of Financing Structure and Modern Tools on Financial Performance: An Analytical Study of a Number of American Banks. *Tikrit University/College of Administration and Economics*, 34-46.
 24. Kinza, A., & Amina, H. (2022). he Role of Modern Financial Analysis in Evaluating a Firm's Financial Performance: A Case Study of the Salt Complex-Al-Wataya. *Faculty of Economics, Business, and Management Sciences*.
 25. Li, Y. (2024). Coping Strategies For Financing Constraints Of Small And Medium-Sized Enterprises (Smes) Under Financial Intelligence Transformation. *Advances In Economics, Management And Political Sciences*, 84-90.
 26. Liberman, A. Paravisini, D. , & Pathania, V. (2018). High-Cost Debt and Perceived Creditworthiness: Evidence from the U.K. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 1-68.
 27. Miečinskienė, S. A., Jurevičienė, T. K., & Gudelytė, Ž. . (2023). The role of financial intelligence quotient and financial literacy for paving a path towards financial well-being. *ournal of Business Economics and Management*, 901-922.
 28. Mohd, R. S., & Kamaruddin, B. (2016). Measuring Financial Intelligence Of Malaysian Gen Y: A Preliminary Study. *World Review Of Business Research*, 157-169.
 29. Mu, P. (2020). Discussion On The Ways To Improve The Financial Intelligence Of Small And Micro Enterprises. In *Journal Of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 1682, No. 1, P. 012074)*. (p. 12074). USA: Iop Publishing.
 30. Muehlburger, M., Rueckel, D., & Koch, S. (2019). A framework of factors enabling digital

transformation, ORGANIZATIONAL TRANSFORMATION & INFORMATION SYSTEMS. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 1-15.

31. Ohelal, I. (2017). Financial Intelligence and Wealth Creation. *International Academies Group*, 2-28.
32. Omoregie, O. K. (2019). Corporate Financial Intelligence As A Driver Of Organizational Performance: A Conceptual And Exploratory Review. *Arabian Journal Of Business And Management Review*, 5-8.
33. Pagani, M., & Pardo, C. (2017). The impact of digital technology on relationships in a business network. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 67, 185-192., 185-192.
34. Safi , S. K., D. ., (2024). Impact Of Senior Management's Financial Intelligence On The Financial Performance Of Banks And Insurance Companies In The Gaza Strip. *Discover Sustainability*, 70-84.
35. SlawTea, h. (2013). The role of information and communication technology in upgrading financial and banking products. *Journal of Economics and Development - Laboratory of Sustainable Local Development - University of Medea*, 1(1), 80-93.
36. Yuniawati, A., & Farman, ., (2023). Analysis Of Financial Reports To Assess Financial Performance. *Jornal Imiah Manajemen, Ekonomi, & Akuntansi (Mea)*, 889-900.